

Emulating the Jezebel Pu-239 Benchmark for Nuclear Data Analysis with Neural Networks

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ABSTRACT

Work done to date on training machine learning models to emulate the Jezebel Plutonium benchmark is presented. Perturbed neutron cross sections are used to simulate Jezebel. A multilayer perceptron neural network is trained on the perturbed cross sections to predict the corresponding values of k_{eff} , and the preliminary results for an early proof-of-concept case is shown (MT=18 only for Pu-239). Finally, the current plan for extending the machine learning (ML) model is presented, including perturbations of other channels and nuclides, and the use of random nuclear data files for training in preparation for use as a tool for accelerating Total Monte Carlo calculations.

Keywords: Nuclear data, machine learning, benchmarks

1. INTRODUCTION

Integral benchmarks are a key component of the nuclear data evaluation process [1]. When validating and analysing nuclear data, these benchmarks are often repeatedly simulated using computationally expensive Monte Carlo radiation transport codes. For some forms of analysis, such as in Total Monte Carlo (TMC) [2], simulations must be run thousands of times to generate statistics and useful analyses of the effects of cross sections and other observables on differential or integral measurements such as spectra or k_{eff} respectively. Depending on the number of iterations, this process can take days and is difficult to integrate into a feedback loop due to its high computational cost.

The use of machine learning methods for emulating benchmark simulations of varying nuclear data inputs has briefly been researched for such analysis [3], but no production-level models have been generated to date. The production of such models entails training a ML algorithm to reproduce the correct values of k_{eff} , neutron fluxes, and other observables measured in the original benchmark experiments as a function of various perturbed nuclear data. The primary aim of such models would be a considerable improvement in the computational time required to run TMC calculations. In addition to the use case of accelerating TMC, accurate ML models of benchmarks may also be useful in the wider nuclear data evaluation process of generating new cross sections, e.g., to integrate feedback and validate libraries due to the increase in the speed of benchmark calculations.

In this work, we present early efforts to build a neutron transport emulator for the Jezebel Pu-239 benchmark using ML methods. These models are to be trained on Monte Carlo-generated data to predict k_{eff} . This is currently proof of concept work, aiming to determine the feasibility of producing ML emulators accurate enough for use in nuclear data analysis and evaluation. As such only limited data for Pu-239 fission and elastic scattering cross sections are currently available, with ongoing efforts to generate more training data representative of the entire Jezebel benchmark. Work is also ongoing to extend models to predict neutron flux spectra.

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2. BACKGROUND AND METHODS

2.1. Jezebel

The Jezebel Plutonium-239 benchmark (PU-MET-FAST-001) [4] consists of a spherical mass with a radius of 6.3849cm, composed of 94.5% Pu-239, 4.5% Pu-240, 0.3% Pu-241 and about 1% natural gallium, with a measured $k_{\text{eff}} = 1.000 \pm 0.002$.

Jezebel has several characteristics making it a favourable model for a proof of concept ML emulator: its fast neutron spectrum reduces its sensitivity to resonances, making the perturbation of resonance parameters unnecessary as k_{eff} has low sensitivity to thermal and epithermal fluxes. Jezebel's geometrical simplicity is also hypothesised to reduce the amount of training data required compared to more geometrically heterogeneous benchmarks. Additionally, Jezebel constitutes of 5 nuclides, only 3 of which are isotopes of plutonium, which is a low enough number to not require a massive amount of nuclide-channel observable combinations (further discussed in Section 2.3). Lastly, Jezebel is an important criticality benchmark frequently cited in new releases of evaluated data libraries.

2.2. SCONE

All Monte Carlo simulations of Jezebel were run using the SCONE transport code [5]. Each simulation run to generate training data used 100 inactive cycles and 5,000 active cycles, with a neutron population of 100,000 for 5×10^7 neutron histories for each simulation. Each simulation resulted in a calculation uncertainty of no more than 5 pcm for k_{eff} .

2.3. Data generation

For this initial study, the fission (MT=18, MF=3) cross sections of Pu-239 are perturbed in groups following the ECCO 33-group structure for fast systems. First, perturbed ACE files and their corresponding PENDFs are generated using the SANDY processing code [6]. These ACE files are used to run perturbed simulations of Jezebel with SCONE, with each run corresponding to a single k_{eff} value, while the values of the cross sections are scraped from the PENDF file, with both together forming a single ML input sample.

In order to produce sufficient informative training data, perturbations ranging from -50% to +50% are applied to each group with spacings of 0.1%, leading to 1,000 samples per energy group. When generating perturbed files, thermal energy groups are binned together due to Jezebel's low k_{eff} sensitivity to thermal neutron flux, although predictions of perturbed thermal or epithermal cross sections are not included in the results section as data processing is ongoing.

Training ML models on simulations where only one observable is perturbed, e.g. Pu-239 fission, may not be sufficient to produce accurate predictions if multiple observables are perturbed simultaneously. In Jezebel, k_{eff} is relatively linear relative to individual group perturbations. Hence, as data generation progresses, simulations for generating training data may be run using perturbed ACE files for multiple nuclides simultaneously, or for channels perturbed simultaneously. This data generation scheme is computationally expensive and leads to a rapidly increasing number of combinations as more observables, e.g. new nuclides or channels, are added to the simulation problem.

Hence, ongoing and future research are also concerned with determining the optimal spacings of perturbations, and the extent to which the entire perturbation domain needs to be represented in the training data whilst maintaining model accuracy. For certain observables, e.g. neutron capture in gallium isotopes, large perturbations to the capture cross sections (e.g. 50%) have little to no statistically significant effect on k_{eff} and may be omitted for the sake of reducing the amount of combinations of perturbations that need to be generated.

Random ACE files and their associated training data are also currently being produced, but are not used at time of writing for training models or testing. These random files will form a key aspect of model training, and a discussion of random data is included due to its relevance to the group-wise perturbations currently being performed. Random files are generated using the reported ENDF/B-VIII.0 MF=33 covariances and normal or lognormal sampling using SANDY. For the data presented in this paper, uncertainties or standard deviations in the Pu-239 (n,f) cross sections are small enough that correction for negative values with lognormal sampling are unnecessary. It is noted that only random files are perturbed using covariances, group perturbations are applied without random sampling.

The intent of using perturbations in groups is twofold: to work as an initial simpler proof of concept for k_{eff} predictions, and to test whether training models on isolated perturbations and eventually random perturbations informed by covariances may be more informative than training solely on random data. In other words, perturbing groups one at a time and leaving the remaining cross sections unperturbed may more easily isolate the effects on k_{eff} , i.e. removing compensating effects of perturbations in other energy groups.

The approach described above for group perturbations and random perturbations using covariances will eventually be extended to more reaction channels, e.g. inelastic neutron scattering, and to other constituent nuclides of Jezebel. These findings may potentially inform the production of future ML models simulating other important benchmarks, such as Godiva.

2.4. Machine Learning Methods

2.4.1. Multilayer Perceptrons

One of the more widely used ML algorithms, Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs) and by extension deep neural networks [7] consist of layers of interconnected nodes, or neurons, which act upon input data as in Eq. (1):

$$\hat{y} = f \left(b + \sum_i w_i x_i \right). \quad (1)$$

The input data are denoted by x_i , with w_i being adjustable weights, b the bias for the particular node, f an activation function used to introduce non-linearity, or to process outputs into a distribution, and \hat{y} the output of the neuron. The input values x_i may be the initial input data (cross sections), or the outputs of neurons in the previous layer of the MLP structure. An illustration of the input data is given in Table I.

Table I. Example of tabulated input data

	$\sigma(E = 0.2 \text{ MeV})$	$\sigma(E = 0.3 \text{ MeV})$...	$\sigma(E = 1.0 \text{ MeV})$
Sample 1	$1.00 \times 10^{-1} \text{ b}$	$2.75 \times 10^{-2} \text{ b}$...	$5.50 \times 10^{-3} \text{ b}$
Sample 2	$1.00 \times 10^{-1} \text{ b}$	$2.50 \times 10^{-2} \text{ b}$...	$5.50 \times 10^{-3} \text{ b}$

It is hypothesised that MLPs' ability to accurately model complex non-linear systems, and their generally fast inference computation both on GPUs and on CPU-only systems, makes them an appropriate candidate for emulating the k_{eff} and flux generation capability of Monte Carlo codes.

At a high level, MLPs are trained by minimising a loss function which measures the distance of a model's output values to known "label" values of a training dataset. Loss functions are modular, with the current loss function used in this work being the mean squared error:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_i^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2, \quad (2)$$

where y_i represents a label value, in this context a SCONE-calculated value of k_{eff} . Although the model predicts a singular value at a time, the value n corresponds to the batch number used in training. This batch number denotes the number of samples used to calculate the loss before weights and biases are updated in each training iteration.

Training itself is an iterative procedure where the aforementioned weights and biases are tuned to decrease the loss. This is done through backpropagation, i.e., calculating the rate of change of the loss function with respect to changes in the values of the weights and biases. Hence when training a model, the algorithm seeks to minimise loss with respect to training data by optimising the values of the tuneable parameters. Other parameters are available for tuning model training and performance, such as the number of layers, the number of neurons per layer, and the aforementioned batch size amongst others. The structure of the latest version of the MLP being used to emulate Jezebel is shown in Table II. Keras [8] is used to build the MLP, with a batch size of 16 and using the Adam optimiser.

Table II. MLP structure

Parameter	Nodes	Activation function
Input layer	200	Linear
Hidden layer 1	150	ReLU
Output layer	1	Linear

2.4.2. Convolutional Neural Networks

Another model algorithm being trialled is the convolutional neural network (CNN). CNNs are typically used for tasks involving multidimensional data where the order or indexing of the data matters, such as with images. CNNs work by using convolutions of small matrices called "filters" or "kernels" with the input data, which in this case are tabulated cross sections, as described in [9]. These convolutions allow a model to collapse the input data into a latent space, with the latter's dimensions depending on the kernel size and the convolution scheme used.

For image processing and other data processing where order in multiple directions matters, each convolution is performed across a higher dimensional subsection of the available data. In the case of tabulated cross sections however, all channel-nuclide observables (e.g. Pu-239 fission or Ga-69 capture) must be considered simultaneously, as there is no clear basis for only performing convolutions over a subset of channel-nuclide observables. In other words, for 1-D CNNs, if 5 reaction channels are included in the training data, convolutions are performed over all 5 channels.

Hence the CNN architecture currently being investigated for this research is the 1-dimensional CNN. The additional tuneable parameters in this case are the size of the kernel (e.g., how many point-wise cross sections to operate on, per matrix multiplication) and the step size across the energy dimension. The current CNN architecture being employed consists (sequentially) of an input layer, a 1-D convolutional layer with 16 kernels of size 3 with ReLU activation, followed by a dense layer with 10 nodes also using ReLU and an output layer with one node using linear activation.

CNNs are hypothesised to provide a suitable architecture due to their ability to collapse large amounts of point-wise cross section data, where individual points may not have much effect on the benchmark outcomes, to more informative latent spaces which are a compression of information from different channels and nuclides.

3. CURRENT RESULTS

As previously covered, ML model predictions shown in this section are restricted to the Pu-239 fission channel as data generation is still ongoing for most channels and for other isotopes of plutonium or gallium. For these preliminary results, a total of 13,011 samples are available representing the fission cross sections of Pu-239, with data included for groups 1 to 14 of the ECCO 33-group structure. For the purposes of this demonstration, lower energy groups (15-33) are omitted as data processing is incomplete at the moment of writing, and the groups in question altogether have relatively small effects on k_{eff} in the order of a few tens of pcm.

Table III presents preliminary results for the MLP and CNN models used so far trained on all available data, as well as results for groups that have been tested individually so far. Inference speed is not reported as model architecture is not finalised, but the prediction time was less than 1s per sample for each model.

Table III. k_{eff} prediction accuracy in groups 1-14 for Pu-239 (n,f) cross sections

Model	Mean absolute error	Std. dev. (absolute)	Max absolute error
MLP (combined groups)	29 pcm	35 pcm	304 pcm
1-D CNN	7 pcm	6 pcm	35 pcm
MLP (group 1 only)	3 pcm	3 pcm	12 pcm
MLP (group 3 only)	8 pcm	6 pcm	29 pcm
MLP (group 4 only)	8 pcm	10 pcm	61 pcm
MLP (group 5 only)	8 pcm	7 pcm	42 pcm
MLP (group 10 only)	6 pcm	4 pcm	20 pcm

Current results show that the current model architecture is more well suited for training on individual groups, and worse performance on the combined data may be due to low model complexity. Overall however, for individual group predictions of k_{eff} , predictions fall close to or within the ± 5 pcm uncertainty of the SCONE calculations themselves. Figure 1 shows prediction error versus the MC-calculated values of k_{eff} for the combined group MLP model, and Figure 2 shows the error plotted against perturbation level.

Figure 1. Error plotted against k_{eff}

Figure 2. Error vs. perturbation level.

Unsurprisingly, models currently struggle more with tail regions where large perturbations (up to 50%)

are applied. Moving forwards, it may be unnecessary to train models on such large perturbations given the aforementioned magnitudes of reported uncertainties in evaluated covariances. In the case of Jezebel Pu-239, randomised Pu-239 data sampled using reported covariances typically yield differences in the hundreds of pcm at most.

It is noted that the number of samples available per group is 1,000 except for group 1 where 1,304 samples were originally generated to result in k_{eff} perturbations of 0.9 to 1.1, before it was decided to restrict perturbations to be closer to criticality. Because of the relatively low amount of training data available, the test data fraction is kept to 10%. Secondly, the only CNN model tested to date was applied to data forming simultaneous perturbations of group 1 Pu-239 fission cross sections, and group 4 Pu-239 elastic scattering cross sections.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the first stages of work towards building ML models capable of predicting k_{eff} for the Jezebel integral benchmark. For small test cases of group perturbations, models have shown an ability to predict k_{eff} with an error in the order of tens of pcm relative to MC transport code calculations, and despite the lack of data and optimisation, larger test cases of thousands of samples are yielding predictions mostly within the original benchmark's uncertainties. Much work is left to be done to both achieve useable accuracy, and to develop models representative of the entire benchmark encompassing the various reaction channels and nuclides present.

5. FUTURE RESEARCH

Beyond this current proof of concept work, further research will involve generating training data for other reaction channels, namely elastic scattering, inelastic scattering, capture, and $(n,2n)$. These data may be generated for the remaining component nuclides of Jezebel prioritising channels and nuclides based on k_{eff} sensitivity.

While only cross sections are currently being investigated, other observables such as outgoing angular distributions are also of interest. In addition to predicting k_{eff} , ML models will also be extended to neutron flux predictions. The main drawback of this ML-based approach, however is the rapidly exploding combinatorial problem as more observables are included in the training data. Generally, ML methods are best at interpolating within the domains of the data they are trained on. Hence to produce reliably accurate models it may be necessary to cover all possible combinations of perturbations, which becomes computationally intractable if too many nuclides, channels, or other observables are introduced. The limits of this ML-based approach are thus to be tested. This will involve testing how many training samples are necessary for accurate results, or what perturbation spacings are necessary for efficient training. These studies will inform whether this is tractable or not, and whether developing ML emulators for other benchmarks would be feasible.

Lastly, also of interest is the effect on accuracy of other ML methods. For now, only MLPs and 1-dimensional CNNs have been investigated, but there is also interest in using a Transformer-based [10] approach for predicting k_{eff} and flux values. Transformers' use of attention functions involves working with correlations between inputs, which could be of use when predicting k_{eff} values and fluxes that are the result of multiple simultaneous perturbations across different channel-nuclide observables.

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